

MINIMIZING EMOTIONAL DISABILITY THROUGH EFFECTIVE RELIGIOUS COUNSELLING EDUCATION IN HIGHER INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

An emotional disability is a disability that impacts a person's ability to effectively recognize, interpret, control, and express fundamental emotions. Staff who exhibit what appear to be mental or emotional issues while in the workplace or performing their duties present some of the most difficult situations with institution. The study examined minimizing emotional disability through effective religious counselling education of higher institutions' staff in Nigeria. It was revealed that emotional disability is a condition exhibiting one or more of the following characteristics over a long period of time and to a marked degree that adversely affects staff performance. This indicate that every educational institute should have counsellor to guide and to help the staff. The counseling services to students and their normal self are good predictors for mental health promotion. However, religious counselling education is capable of influencing people social and emotional change. Religious Counseling education stimulates more self-driven vigor and capability for living to societal norms and upholding ethical standard. Religious Counseling service helps in emotional issues to shape people's behaviour where it states that it is a hallmark that student's behaviour modification rests on. However, there is significant relationship between counseling education and people emotional disturbance and mental health promotion. Therefore, religious counselling services should be provided in every higher institution to manage all forms of emotional disability among staff. A qualified religious person who can pray and devote his/her time should be appointed for counselling; he should be available for them so they can freely consult him/her.

Keywords: Counseling, Disability, Emotional, Minimizing, Religious

Introduction

People have major concerns on their mind that may interfere with their success, happiness, and satisfaction in their lives. People with disabilities are an extremely diverse group, each with unique learning strengths and needs. Despite the ever-increasing need, these people are frequently misunderstood and underserved by the counseling profession (Duncan & Sojourner, 2013). Federal laws, such as the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) and the Individuals with Disabilities Act (IDEA), have made serving people with disabilities an issue of legal significance. Their mental balance is needed in many situations. Such as family problems, homesickness, identity, loneliness, loss of motivation, pain, problems with food or body image. When people cannot cope with the situations, they lose their emotional mental health. In developing countries, the decline of mental health has increased and neglects the social dimensions, family and personal

touches remained the irreversible effects (Dadsetan, 2008). It has been reported that person-centred counseling is effective for clients with common mental health problems such as anxiety and depression. As a result, it has become necessary for counselors to better understand the issues regarding people with disabilities, including the ability to recognize disabilities and the differing forms of treatment (Currie & Kahn, 2012). Increased knowledge and experience are essential for counselors who wish to better serve people with disabilities and their families.

Counseling is a way of helping people to solve their emotional, social, personal or interpersonal problems. Counseling is not giving advice, or solving your problems on your behalf. In counseling, counsellor guides you to look at problems with objective way. He shows different dimension to understand the situation. He helps you to know your strengths and weaknesses without being judgmental (Khodaei, 2007). Counseling involves the exploration of problems in an environment that is both supportive and objective. It also involves the identification of alternative courses of action that might solve a problem. Counselor suggests strategies for managing and altering patterns of upsetting thoughts, feelings and behaviour.

Globally, counseling services are essential elements in discipline and management of people in all societies. It could be difficult for any society to function well when they “are” emotional disturbed or without the exercise of discipline (UNESCO, 2017). Counseling services as a movement started in America at the beginning of the 20th Century as a reaction to change process in an industrialized society. Counseling services were set up within the department of education in September 1968 when the recommendations made by Louis, a consultant sent over to Malta by United Nation’s Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), were taken up Summit (2017). Counseling is formalized actions taken by the society to make operations available to people. These services have been delimited by common agreements to provide a unique action which overlap minimally with other school functions. Counseling service is based on the fact that everybody at one time or the other need helps. So, this help should be rendered unconditionally with empathy understand and free atmosphere. Also, these services promote the personal-social planning and programming for student with special skills that helps to achieve the goals needed in the school setting and to be emotional stable (UNESCO, 2016). However, the paper examined reducing emotional disturbance through instrumentality of counseling education in Nigeria.

Concept of Counseling

According to Willey and Andrew (2011), counseling involves two individuals, one seeking help and the other a professionally trained person who helps to solve problems, orient and direct him towards a goal which leads to his maximum development and growth. Counseling services are therefore required for individuals having developmental problems because of the handicap they suffer in any area of emotion either because of hereditary factors or “environment” conditions. Counseling is an integral part of an over-all programme of guidance. Counseling is a process designed to help clients understand and clarify personal views of their life space, and to learn to reach their self-determined goals through meaningful, well-informed choices and a resolution of problems of an emotional or interpersonal nature. It believes that every individual has the potential for self-growth, self-development and self-actualization (Ndum & Onukwuga, 2013).

Counseling Education

Counseling Education mainly refers to providing assistance and guidance to students in making the right choices in their studies, in their educational plans, career aspirations, choice of stream and specialization as well as the selection of college or university as per their interests and preferences (Busari, 2015). Educational Counseling has an important role in every student's life as it helps them make informed decisions at every step of their academic and professional journey. Many people think that we do not need any professional guidance in our educational or career quest but the right mentor can transform your life (Williams-Oladapo,2024). Counseling is a way of helping people solving emotional, social, personal or interpersonal problems. Counselling is not giving advice, or solving your problems on your behalf.

In counseling, counsellor guides you to look at problems with objective way. He shows different dimension to understand the situation. He helps you to know your strengths and weaknesses without being judgmental. Counselling involves the exploration "of the" problems in an environment that is both supportive and objective. It also involves the identification of alternative courses of action that might solve a problem. Counselor suggests strategies for managing and altering patterns of upsetting thoughts, feelings and behaviour. An Educational Counselor mainly works with school and college students in academic environments. Many schools have their own educational counselors to help students find the right career and make informed choices in their studies especially special needs children and educational counsellors also assist students in dealing with the personal issues impacting their academic journey (Busari, 2015). To resolve such issues and Educational Counsellor also interacts with the student's parents or guardian or teachers to help them in figuring out the best solutions for the student's problems.

History and Development of Counseling Education

The development of guidance and counseling started in Nigeria for various reasons which include: expansion in the enrollment of pupils in the primary and secondary schools after the independence in 1960, the growing need of youth in Nigeria, repeated changes in the education system and unrest in tertiary institutions and the changes in home and family life (F GN, 2014 edition). According to Ndum and Onukwugha (2013) and Omoniyi (2016), it is generally accepted that in Nigeria the organized and formal guidance and counseling service started in 1959 at St. Theresa's College, Oke Ado Ibadan, by a group of dedicated religious sisters who had the perception of the need for proper guidance in job selection for their secondary school leavers. They invited some "professionals who are not members of the school community, to interact with the final year students" This is about eight decades after the birth of an established and functional guidance and counselling services in America. "This advice formed the beginning of Nigeria Career Counselling"

The Federal Ministry of Education in its efforts to encourage guidance education established a guidance counselling unit in 1961 and employed an education officer named Mr C. I. Berepeki to serve as Vocational Guidance Officer in the Federal Ministry of Education. This official gesture went a long way to stimulate and promote a steady interest in professional guidance and counseling in the then Western Nigeria which established an Advanced Teachers' College of Education named Olunloyo College of Education. The College was staffed with a team of experts in Education and Counselling from Ohio State University "and" United State of America. Such group of lecturers according to records included the eminent personalities in counseling.

According to Akinboye in Owuamanam (2007), the first series of Nigeria Diploma Certificate in Counselling were awarded in this college and the beneficiaries of these awards were the first cream of teacher/career masters and counsellors that arose in Nigeria. Akinboye in (Owuamanam (2007) noted that the first workshop on Vocational. Guidance Counselling and Testing in Nigeria was organized in 1964 by the Federal Ministry of Education. This brought all the career masters and all the potential guidance counsellors under various voluntary organizations together. The first indigenous Department of Guidance and Counselling was established at the University of Ibadan in 1975; and the inauguration of the Counselling Association of Nigeria in 1976 at the same University of Ibadan as an affiliation of the American Personnel and Guidance Association (APGA). The Federal Government then inserted the need for guidance and counselling services and courses in our schools in National Policy on Education by 1981. This then led the state governors to establish guidance and counselling units in their ministries of education, in addition to counselling units in the universities (Ugwu, 2008).

Emotional Disability

Employees who exhibit what appear to be mental or emotional issues while in the workplace or performing their duties present some of the most difficult situations for employers. They may have a disability you may be required to accommodate under the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA). They also may, at times at least, be unable to satisfactorily perform their job duties. Determining what rights, they have, and what obligations you have under the ADA, can be very challenging.

Religious Education

Religious education is a lesson, instruction or coaching of a specific religion. In contemporary and secular society, religious education involves a particular kind of teaching which is so much not associated with the academic world and usually considers religious faith as the basic ideology and working modality, as well as a required condition of attendance. We can also say that religious education is a phrase given to education concerned with the study of religion. It can be referred to the teachings achieved through a church or religious association for information with regards to doctrinal beliefs and faith, or for learning in various areas of religion, but with no unequivocally religious or ethical aspires, e.g. in a school, college or university. The expression frequently has common characteristics with religious studies. (Wikipedia, 2010)

Purpose Of Religious Education Curriculum

The Religious Education syllabus is designed to provide students with opportunities to participate in the age-long search of human beings for the meaning and purpose of life, and to facilitate an appreciation and an affirmation of their own sense of uniqueness and identity. It is intended to assist them in understanding the concept of God in religions. It also seeks to help them become aware of the interconnectedness among God, human beings and the world. The syllabus exposes students to different religious ideas, values and ways of expressing them so that they can interact meaningfully with people of different religious and cultural persuasions in the world.

Further, the syllabus seeks to foster understanding, appreciation and respect for the religious, ethnic, cultural, political and other aspects of plurality in the Caribbean. It is intended that the study of the Religious Education syllabus will help students to understand their society and the

belief systems of others, clarify their own belief systems, deal with problems, and resolve conflicts.

This syllabus will contribute to the development of the Ideal people, by promotions and encouraging the cross-pollination of ideas among students of different ethnic backgrounds, cultures and points of view. The syllabus will also help students to develop intellectually and seeks to refine their critical thinking skills and judgments and the acquisition of skills as defined in the UNESCO pillars of Learning through research and the study of four world religions and indigenous religions found in the world.

Aims of Religious Education Curriculum

The aims of religious education is to:

1. Develop an understanding of the meaning and purpose of life as advanced by different religions practiced in the world;
2. Encourage informed dialogue among various cultural and religious organizations and groups to foster harmony and peace among people of diverse customs and beliefs within the society;
3. Encourage a critical and reflective approach to religious beliefs and practices;
4. Encourage appreciation and respect for various belief systems;
5. Create an awareness of the diversity and communality that exist in religion;
6. Create an awareness of our religious heritage

Reducing Emotional Disability through the Instrumentality of Religious Counseling Education

Religious counselling education is intended to assist people in understand themselves, others, environment and achieve capability to adjust accordingly. The need for counseling education cannot be underestimated. This is as a result of the increasingly intricacy of modern life that have bestowed weighty demands and responsibilities on people. These individuals are faced with diverse needs and problems which when unattended to could metamorphose into undesirable behaviours (Weiten, 2007). Religious counseling programmes were therefore introduced to help people overcome and adjust to a swarm of social and emotional challenges they encounter at home and the society. Counselling education ensures that people's social and emotional crisis are checked and managed side by side with their daily activities in the society.

The challenges facing people if not checked is capable of derailing them from their daily pursuit. In this wise, Makinde (2014) singled out a steady and disquieting problem as that of relational distinction among people and other element in the environment. Horgan (2003) posited that despite the seemingly increasing relational challenges faced by people, the counselors have more impact in enhancing peoples' interpersonal social and emotional values. Conger and Peterson (2014) added that counselors contribute to peoples' behaviour change through imparting and retaining interpersonal values. Such values include showing reciprocal respect to all people, and forbearance especially in times of challenges. Also, Theodore (2012) noted that religious counselors use individual or group counselling strategies to assist people especially students obtain social values. Stewart (2013) observed that religious counselors help in providing social values which tend to proliferate students' healthy relations amongst themselves and other persons in their environment for easy adjustment

Waiten (2007) perceived that social and emotional disturbance or adjustment among secondary school students is the most intense and vital experience that transform into the change of behaviour. Thus, giving credence for the need to channel this energy into productive venture, he stated further that school life is riddle with things that can become maddening and that they are beyond students control; hence the need for experienced hand to guide the students in their activities. According to Dondo (2004), secondary school students experience anger at different times as a result of poor academic achievement, clash between them and fellow students, teachers, parents, amongst others. Hurlock (2007) opined that school religious counselors emerge highly in helping students learn to control their fury in a bid to adjust meaningfully to their social worlds. Collins (2007) stated that when resentment is controlled in the right ways, it can be a tool that channel students' energy towards positive ventures that will enhance their academic standing. Kabiru and Njenga (2009) have observed that individual crisis counseling in schools help students to check their rage and use appropriate strategies that positively impacts on their general well-being. Gichaga (2006) highlighted some of the rage management strategies thought to students by guidance counselors as comprehending the cause and nature of their fury, voiced out and vent their rage-related feelings beneficially, and being mindful in an attempt to stop anger. Collins (2007) views counselors as people with skills that help in influencing students' commitment in the process leading to productive transformation in the right way. As such, school counselors play vital role in helping students to understand and apply the most appropriate ways of managing their anger which is the most multifaceted feelings in the range of human sentiment (Dondo, 2004).

Wanjama, (2006) in their study identified educational counseling services as key to influencing students' management of their social and emotional reactions which mostly determine the character of the individual student. Karega (2008) opined that erudition in secondary schools is often interrupted by the unusual behavioural patterns of students. Dryafol (2002) posited that secondary school students carry along with them a host of juvenile challenges which are erratic physiological changes ensuing to impulsive mood swings, with social and emotional changes that are evident. He implication here is that they become rebellious to constituted authority. Sindabi (1992) postulates, that, "young people in secondary schools undergo social and emotional development, manifesting personality of being erratic, unpredictable, ambivalent, rebellious", amongst others, giving credence to the veracity of guidance and counseling services in secondary schools. In the opinion of Rao (2002), guidance and counselling services can help clarify to the student's better ways of managing their social and emotional adjustment and making sure that they are at best constructive and integrative. He noted that a socially and emotionally well-adjusted student via counselling should be able to minimize disintegrative emotions while magnifying integrative one.

In research on high school counseling services conducted by some researchers (Razmi, 2019), the conclusion reached in the consultative services to help students have been effective. Research results (Baum and Fleming, 2013) show that counseling services in schools has led to resolve the academic problems. In Ardabil Province, Khodaei (2007) showed that effect of group counseling in decreasing students anxiety is promising. Hoseynnezhad (2017) as well as similar research conducted on depressed students and showed that male students decreased depression. Gamari (2011) has also stated that the greatest problems in students are interpersonal problems, anxiety and depression and their advisers need to see more training. Other than the above reports, the

effects of counseling services on students' mental health, not studied much, but a close investigation as factors in the success of consultants in providing consultative services desired, is executed. Samadpoor (2011) reported the factors such as age, condition and appearance of document related consulting services to confirm the effectiveness of consultative services. Most theories of counseling and psychotherapy, have been intended mental health and promote it to various methods (Shafiabady, 2019). In this study, all the theories and methods of effective counseling and psychotherapy, have been cited reference.

Researches conducted on the effectiveness of counseling services on students' mental health has reached similar results (Ragibi, 2013; Asadi, 2011). Results of this experiment regarding the significant reduction in the social interaction and depression are consistent with the results of Milin and et al (2010), Ragibi (2013), and Asgharipur and Jahanrafat (2011) and Hoseynnezhad (2017). According to the theories, depression and social difficulties skills are issues that more respond to psychological counseling interventions. Of course, having expertise in the field of psychology and counseling is necessary, because the mental health of students improved significantly under the experiment, mostly due to the intervention of consultants have been of psychological education. Means the presence of the same issue with the educational non-psychology consultants can answer one of the reasons for not giving somatization and anxiety, insomnia, students will be considered. Difficulty in treating problems such as short-term psychosomatic disorder, another reason may come into account. Researchers like as part of their studies have found similar results. Results showed a high correlation between gender adviser and the student's overall score in mental health scale. Perhaps this conclusion was attributed to the seriousness of women in resolving the students' problems. Another possible cause of this result, which has been tested, is the field advisor. Women more than men had a psychology of education.

Conclusion

In conclusion, emotional disability is a condition exhibiting one or more of the following characteristics over a long period of time and to a marked degree that adversely affects staff performance. The findings of this study indicate that every educational institute should have counsellor to guide and to help the staff. The counselling services to students and their normal self are good predictors for mental health promotion. However, counselling education is capable of influencing people social and emotional change. Counseling education stimulates more self-driven vigor and capability for living to societal norms and upholding ethical standard. Counseling service helps in emotional issues to shapes people behaviour where it states that it is a hallmark that students behaviour modification rests on. However, there is significant relationship between counseling education and people emotional disturbance and mental health promotion.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that;

1. Counseling services should be provided in every Federal Educational Institution. A qualified person should be appointed for counselling to students and when they need help, he should be available for students so they can freely consult their counsellor.
2. Government should create a counselling section in every public secondary school in the state and employ seasoned counselors to man them as this will help students balance their academics with social and emotional issues.

3. The government should as a matter of urgency establish well functional Counselling units in Institution of learning.
4. Fiscal support should be given to the establishment of counseling services by both the Federal and State government like other arms of educational support institutions. This would assist in the effective running of the programme.
5. Enlightening and creating awareness concerning the aims and objectives of counselling education should be carried out by the Ministry of Education at both federal and state levels. This would clarify the minds of the members of staff concerning the wrong notion they already have and enhance their support in achieving the aims and objectives of the guidance and counselling programme. This is important more so that the guidance and counselling

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